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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarizes the results of all the evaluation activities performed during the project.

The evaluation activities of the OIKONET project have focused on three main areas:

- **Events:** the 3 project general meetings, the 18 subnetwork meetings, and the 3 OIKONET international conferences on “Global dwelling” have been evaluated. The goal of these evaluations was to assess the event’s effectiveness in reaching the project outcomes, their impact on stakeholders and the satisfaction of participants.
- **Learning activities:** 8 Learning Spaces (in some cases in their different editions) and the 3 international workshops and the corresponding preparatory activities in the learning spaces have been evaluated. The goals of these evaluations were to assess the effectiveness of the learning activities, the achievement of the learning outcomes, the overall learning and teaching process, and the effectiveness of the integration of the digital tools into the learning and teaching processes.
- **Digital environment:** the OIKONET digital environment has been evaluated through online questionnaires, through an analysis of the usages of the different tools that have been used during the project as communication and collaboration tools, and through a usability analysis of the OIKONET web portal.

Furthermore, two external experts were invited to review some project activities; they participated in some events in the second part of the project and gave their feedback in three reports.

As regards the events, the evaluations showed that the subnetwork and general meetings and the international conferences have been highly appreciated: the meetings were found useful, productive and inspiring; the conferences provided interesting opportunities for networking and promoted a change in the professional practices of participants. One problematic aspect that could not be completely solved was the fact that not all partners were equally engaged and active in the meetings nor in the project as a whole.

The evaluations of the learning activities showed that both the online Learning Spaces and the onsite international workshops have been appreciated by both teachers and students. Students’ expectations about the OIKONET proposed learning activities mainly concerned networking, collaboration and communication opportunities. From the students’ feedbacks, the importance of an adequate planning of the online learning activities and of a good alignment of them with the international workshops, when necessary, clearly emerged. Interestingly, the learning activities promoted within OIKONET have also been used by teachers as a space for experimentation both to explore new subject-matters and new learning and teaching methods. Finally, the definition of the expected learning outcomes of the OIKONET learning activities helped both students and teachers to focus on their most important goals.

The different activities of evaluation of the OIKONET digital environment showed that there has been a continuous improvement in terms of usability of the website and of efficiency and effectiveness in the use of the tools for communication and collaboration. The main unresolved critical point about the use of digital tools is the fact that social networks have not been fully exploited to promote and disseminate the project and its results.

Most of the evaluation activities that were planned in Deliverable 6.1 have been performed, even beyond the original plans (for instance, more Learning Spaces than planned have been evaluated, and the usability analysis has been performed on the whole OIKONET website –

also with the help of an eye-tracking tool –, and not only on Oikonetwork). On the contrary, in some other cases some planned activities have not been run (for instance, for exhibitions and for community participation activities).

The main lessons learnt from the evaluation activities can be summarized as follows:

- The participation of the project partners in the evaluation activities has been generally high.
- The results of the evaluations have often been used to improve and refine other project activities.
- The methods and tools that have been used for the evaluations proved to be useful, but in some cases a wider variety of methods could have been of help.
- The importance of involving the evaluation team in the planning of project activities that have to be evaluated emerged clearly during the project.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

According to the project work program, the aim of the present document is to “analyse the overall network performance. It will summarize the results of all the evaluation activities performed during the project. This final report will focus mainly on an evaluation of the general impact of the project activities onto the intended target communities.”

This report presents first a summary of all the evaluation activities that have been carried out during the project, comparing the performed activities to the Evaluation Plan (Deliverable 6.1) that was prepared at the beginning of the project, and explaining – when necessary – the reasons of the deviations from it.

Then, the report presents an analysis of the most remarkable findings that emerged from all the evaluation activities, focussing on how these findings have been used to refine and improve the activities of the OIKONET network in the other work packages and on the impact of the OIKONET project onto the partners’ activities. In this section, the reviews made by the two external evaluators (Prof. Flora Samuel, and Prof. Constantin Spiridonidis) are also included.

Finally, some final considerations about the evaluation activities and the adopted methods will be drawn, to highlight what went well and which problems and difficulties the evaluation team encountered while performing the evaluations.

2.2 Contribution of partners

As leader of WP6 Quality Assurance, USI has been responsible for the production of this deliverable.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

As the evaluation activities described in this document deal with the events, activities and products, which are included in all the work packages, this report concerns the overall OIKONET project and project members.

3 SUMMARY OF THE EVALUATION ACTIVITIES

The evaluation activities of the OIKONET project have focussed on three main areas:

1. **Events:** The project events that have been evaluated include 3 project general meetings, 18 sub-network meetings, and 3 OIKONET international conferences on “Global dwelling”. The goal of these evaluations was to assess the event’s effectiveness in reaching the project outcomes, their impact on stakeholders and the satisfaction of participants.
2. **Learning activities:** Among the learning activities, 8 Learning Spaces have been evaluated, in some cases in different editions; furthermore, the three international workshops and the corresponding preparatory activities in the learning spaces have been evaluated as well.
3. **Digital environment:** The OIKONET digital environment has been evaluated through an online questionnaires, through an analysis of the usages of the different tools that have been used during the project as communication and collaboration tools, and through a usability analysis of the OIKONET web portal.

For most of the above-mentioned evaluation activities, specific reports have been produced and shared with partners. The results of all the evaluation activities have been presented and discussed in the following deliverables:

- Deliverable 6.2 – Evaluation of events, submitted at m18 and m36;
- Deliverable 6.3 – Evaluation of learning activities, submitted at m18 and m36;
- Deliverable 6.4 – Evaluation of the digital environment, submitted at m18 and m36.

Furthermore, following the recommendation of the EACEA after the OIKONET Progress Report, two **external experts** were invited to review some of the project activities; they participated in some events in the second part of the project and produced three reports with their feedback on the observed activities. The OIKONET Steering Committee produced a report with the answers to the comments and remarks exposed in the reports of the external evaluators. The main findings emerged through these evaluation activities are discussed in Chapter 4 of this deliverable.

3.1 Evaluation of events

The following table, presented in Deliverable 6.2, summarizes the evaluation activities that have been conducted on the project events:

Table 1. OIKONET events that have been evaluated

Event		When	Evaluation	Response Rate
Sub-network meetings – Round 1	WP2 – Preston	19.12.2013	Online Survey	61.5% (8 out of 13)
	WP3 – Barcelona	07.02.2014	Online Survey	100% (8 out of 8)
	WP4 – Barcelona	10.01.2014	Online Survey	75% (15 out of 20)
Sub-network meetings – Round 2	WP2 – Ljubljana	16-17.06.2014	Online Survey	83.3% (10 out of 12)
	WP3 – Rimini	27.06.2014	Online Survey	80% (8 out of 10)
	WP4 – Lisbon	16-18.07.2014	Online Survey	50% (12 out of 24)
General Meeting	Barcelona	25-27.09.2014	Online Survey	69% (29 out of 42)
1 st International Conference	Barcelona	25-26.09.2014	Paper Survey	79.1% (34 out of 43)
Sub-network meetings – Round 3	WP2 – Budapest	12-13.12.2014	Online Survey	60% (9 out of 15)
	WP3 – Bratislava	27.02.2015	Online Survey	63.6% (7 out of 11)
	WP4 – Istanbul	30.01.2015	Online Survey	77.8% (14 out of 18)
Sub-network meetings – Round 4	WP2 – Rotterdam	05.06.2015	Online Survey	61.5% (8 out of 13)
	WP3 – Tirana	19.06.2015	Online Survey	30% (3 out of 10)
	WP4 – Cottbus	31.05-03.06.2015	Online Survey	68.2% (15 out of 22)
2 nd General Meeting	Bratislava	24-26.09.2015	Online Survey	65.7% (23 out of 35)
2 nd International Conference	Bratislava	25.09.2015	Paper Survey	56.3% (27 out of 48)
Sub-network meetings – Round 5	WP2 – Zagreb	20.11.2015	Online Survey	61.5% (8 out of 13)
	WP3 – Skopje	18.12.2015	Online Survey	All 4 institutions
	WP4 – Brussels	22-23.01.2016	Online Survey	71.4% (15 out of 21)
Sub-network meetings – Round 6	WP2 – Riga	22.04.2016	Online Survey	5 out of 6 institutions
	WP3 – Barcelona	04.03.2016	Online Survey	85.7% (6 out of 7)
	WP4 – Belgrade	05-09.06.2016	Online Survey	12 out of 17 institutions
3 rd General Meeting	Manchester	22.09.2016	--	--
3 rd International Conference	Manchester	23.09.2016	Paper Survey	57.6% (34 out of 59)

The goal of these evaluations was to assess the event's effectiveness in reaching the project outcomes, their impact on stakeholders and the satisfaction of participants.

Different target groups have been involved in the evaluation activities:

- Subnetwork meetings and general meetings: all project partners who participated in the meetings;
- International conferences: all project partners who attended the conference, invited external speakers, external participants in the conference.

The questionnaire used for the evaluation of the subnetwork and of the general meetings was based on the following template, with small adaptations made in some cases to meet the specific meeting's goals:

- **Meeting Expectations**
 - 1) What were your expectations of this meeting? → open text answers
 - 2) To what extent have these expectations been met? → open text answers
- **Evaluation of Meeting's Sessions**
 - 3) Please award all the MEETING SESSIONS a rating on a scale of 1 to 10 (where 10 is the best) and add any comments you wish.
 - a) SESSION 1
 - b) SESSION 2
 - c) SESSION 3
 - d) SESSION n
- **Overall Rating**
 - 4) How would you rate the meeting overall?
→ rating on scale from 1-10 & comment
- **Meeting Preparation**
 - 5) Did you receive adequate information about the meeting before the meeting began? (e.g. purpose, agenda, venue, accommodation, participants, ...)

→ yes/no with comment explain choice
 - 6) How useful do you consider the preparation activities / tasks before the meeting?

→ scale from 1 (not at all) to 10 (very much) with possibility to add a text comment
- **Suggestions & Name**
 - 7) Do you have any suggestions for the work of the Pedagogical Activities Network?
 - 8) Any other comments or suggestions for future meetings?
 - 9) Name (not mandatory)

Questionnaire for the evaluation of sub-network and general meetings

The questionnaire used for the evaluation of the three international conferences was based on the following template, with small adaptations made to meet the specific conference programs:

Title of the conference

Date, Place

*This questionnaire is to help us evaluate the effectiveness of this conference and the impact of OIKONET. Your responses will be important in helping us to guide further developments of the OIKONET network, and will be stored **anonymously** and analysed. The results summary will be available from the project website, www.oikonet.org.*

Background information

1. Name (optional):
2. Sex: Male / Female
3. Age range: 20-25 / 26-30 / 31-40 / 41-50 / 51-60 / 60-70/ over 70
4. Which town / country are you from? Please identify below:
5. What is your role and discipline? Please underline or specify those which apply
University Teacher / Post Graduate Student / Undergraduate Student / Other (Please, specify)
Architecture / Urban Planning / Pedagogy / Other (Please, specify)

6. What attracted you to the conference?						
7. How did you come to know about this event? Please underline by email / project portal (www.oikonet.org) / project blogs / internet (other blogs,...) / through a friend or colleague / newspaper or magazine / newsletter / Other (Please, specify)						
Event Evaluation:						
Please score each criteria according to the values given below. We would appreciate any comments or thoughts giving more information about the reasons for your score:						
	Event evaluation questions A – strongly agree, B – agree, C - disagree, D – strongly disagree, E – don't know	A	B	C	D	E
9	It was easy to find information on this event					
	<i>Comments</i>					
10	The event was well organised	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
11	I found the selection of presentations appropriate for the conference	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
12	I found the presentations interesting	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
13	The conference has increased my knowledge about the OIKONET project	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
14	The event provided opportunities for networking	A	B	C	D	E
	<i>Comments</i>					
15	Will you change anything in your teaching, research or working practices, thanks to the attendance of the conference? If yes, please specify.					
	<i>Comments</i>					
16	What did you like about this event?					
	<i>Comments</i>					
17	What could have been done better?					
	<i>Comments</i>					
18	Do you have any other comments?					
	<i>Comments</i>					
19	Are you interested in using the OIKONET tools or in joining the OIKONET network?					
20	If you are interested in receiving more information about any of the below please underline and leave your email address.					
	- the OIKONET project?	Name:				
	- using the OIKONET Workspaces	Email address:				
	- using the OIKONET Case Repository					

Questionnaire for the evaluation of international conferences

3.2 Evaluation of learning activities

The following table, presented in Deliverable 6.3, summarizes the evaluation activities that have been conducted on the OIKONET learning activities:

Table 2. OIKONET learning activities that have been evaluated

Learning Activity	Evaluation	Response Rate
LS “Civic Housing”	1 st round (WS 13/14) by LaSalle	Not evaluated
	2 nd round (SS 15/16) by DIT	No responses
LS “Introduction to Housing”	1 st round (SS 13/14) by UPV Online Survey for UPV Students	25 responses
	2 nd round (WS 15/16) by UPV Online Survey for UPV & ITU students	22 responses (20 UPV & 2 ITU) - report
	3 rd round (SS 15/16) by UPV Online Survey for UPV, ITU & ISCTE students	23 responses (16 UPV, 5 ITU & 2 ISCTE)
LS “Habitat Regeneration Strategies”	WS 14/15; by FASTU – Online survey for FASTU & FAVSUACE students	91 responses (90 FASTU & 1 FAVSUACE) - presentation
LS “Housing Systems”	WS 14/15; by LaSalle – Online survey for LaSalle students	4 responses - report
LS “Threshold Matters”	WS 14/15; by KUL – Online survey for KUL students	18 responses –summary report
LS “Urban Systems”	WS 15/16; by LaSalle – Online survey for LaSalle students	6 responses - report
LS “Urban Housing Regeneration”	WS 15/16; by DIT – Online survey for DIT students	5 responses (out of 20) - report
LS “Small is Power”	1 st round (WS 15/16); by KUL – Online survey for KUL students	2 responses (out of 18) - report
	2 nd round (SS 15/16); by KUL – Online survey for KUL students	7 responses
LS “Thinking Dwelling”	WS & SS 15/16 – Online survey for participating teachers	100% (6 out of 6)
Annual Workshop (Lisbon - 2014)	Paper Survey for Students	95.7% (45 out of 47)
	Online Survey for Teachers	47.0% (11 out of 23)
LS “Contemporary Living Patterns” (SS 13/14)	Online Survey for Teachers	10 responses
	Paper Survey for Students (section within Lisbon Workshop survey)	95.7% (45 out of 47)
Annual Workshop (Cottbus – 2015)	Paper Survey for Students	98.1% (51 out of 52)
	Online Survey for Teachers	14 resp.
LS “Contemporary Living Patterns: Growth / Shrinkage” (SS 14/15)	Paper Survey for Students (section within Cottbus Workshop survey)	98.1% (51 out of 52)
	Section within Cottbus Workshop survey for Teachers	14 resp.

	Short interviews with teachers	8 interviews
Annual Workshop (Belgrade – 2016)	Paper Survey for Students	81.1% (43 out of 53)
	Online Survey for Teachers	12 resp.
LS "Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating livable cities"	Paper Survey for Students (section within Belgrade Workshop survey)	81.1% (43 out of 53)
	Online Survey for Teachers (section within Belgrade Workshop survey)	12 resp.

The main goal of these evaluations was to assess the effectiveness of the integration of the digital tools into the learning and teaching processes. As presented in the Evaluation Plan (Deliverable 6.1), this was evaluated in terms of the students' satisfaction about the achievement of the learning outcomes and the overall learning experience, about the blend of online and in class activities, about distance collaboration activities (when applicable), and about the structure of online activities.

To evaluate the learning activities proposed in the OIKONET Learning Spaces, several surveys have been created and sent to the respective target groups. Each survey was based on the same model, already defined at the beginning of the project in the Evaluation Plan (Deliverable 6.1). However, as Learning Spaces evolved during the project, it has been necessary to adapt the questionnaires to fit each LS by modifying, omitting or adding questions. Whenever possible, the online surveys were distributed to the students and teachers immediately after the end of the learning activities they were involved in.

This is an example of the questionnaires used to collect the feedback of students participating in the Learning Space "Introduction to Housing" (WS 15/16):

This survey wants to gather feedback on the participation in your course related to the OIKONET Workspace "Introduction to Housing" and the use of the OIKONET online environment (Workspace "Introduction to Housing") within this course.

Dear students,

We kindly ask you to give us your feedback on the participation in your course related to the OIKONET Workspace "Introduction to Housing". Your feedback is very important for us, as it allows us to improve future collaborative online learning activities and the use of the OIKONET online Workspace environment.

Thank you very much for your contribution,
The OIKONET evaluation team

COURSE EVALUATION

- 1) What did you **learn** from the participation in the course related to the OIKONET Workspace "Introduction to Housing"? Please, list up to 3 things you have learned from this experience.
- 2) What were your **expectations** regarding the participation in the course related to the OIKONET Workspace "Introduction to Housing"?
- 3) To what extent have these expectations been met? (Only partially; Somewhat; Fully met; It exceeded my expectations) (Make a comment on your choice here).
- 4) How well has the OIKONET online environment (Workspace "Introduction to Housing") been **integrated** into the course at your university? Please, motivate your answer. (Scale from 1 (not at all) to 10 (very well) and free comment)
- 5) What was the added value of the OIKONET online environment "Introduction to Housing" for the course in your university?

- 6) Has working online collaboratively with students / teachers from other countries been a good experience? What did you like and what not? Did you encounter any problems? (Scale from 1 (not at all) to 10 (very well) and free comment)
- 7) How could collaborative learning between students / teachers of other universities be further improved?
- 8) What can we do to create a feeling of real international collaboration among students / teachers from different universities, without them ever meeting face-to-face?
- 9) How useful was the OIKONET online environment (Workspace "Introduction to Housing") for the collaborative learning experience? (Scale from 1 (not at all) to 10 (very well) and free comment)
- 10) Did students / teachers of other universities comment on your work? If yes, did you find their comments useful? Please, motivate your answer. What did you learn from the comments they did to your work? (Nobody commented on my work; scale from 1 (not at all useful) to 10 (very useful) and free comment)
- 11) Did you comment on the work of others? If yes, did you find commenting on others work a useful way of collaborating? Please, motivate your answer. What did you learn by commenting the work of students from other schools? (I did not comment on others' works; Scale from 1 (not at all useful) to 10 (very useful) and free comment)
- 12) Was there any contact with students from other schools? If yes, did some useful relations emerge from the collaborative activities? Will you stay in contact with one or more of the students/teachers of other universities for learning / studying purposes? Please, motivate your answer.
- 13) In the OIKONET online environment (Workspace "Introduction to Housing") were the tasks relevant and clear? Was the sequence of tasks meaningful to you? Please, motivate your answer.
- 14) Do you think the task-based structure of the OIKONET online environment (Workspace "Introduction to Housing") offers a good way of learning?
- 15) Did you get enough training to work efficiently with the OIKONET online environment (Workspace "Introduction to Housing")? (Scale from 1 (not at all) to 10 (very well) and free comment)
- 16) Did you use other collaboration tools besides the OIKONET online environment (e.g. Twitter, Facebook, ...)? If yes, which ones and what for?
- 17) Overall, how easy was it to use the OIKONET online environment (Workspace "Introduction to Housing")? (Scale from 1 (not at all) to 10 (very well) and free comment)
- 18) Do you think this learning experience is worth to be repeated in the future? Please, motivate your answer.
- 19) Do you have any other comments or suggestions?

DEMOGRAPHICS

- 20) University
- 21) Gender
- 22) Name

Questionnaire for the evaluation of the Learning Space "Introduction to housing"

An example of a questionnaire that was used to collect the students' feedback about the three international workshops and the corresponding preparatory learning activities is included in Annex 1 (Evaluation questionnaire for the Belgrade international workshop).

To collect the feedback of teachers about the international workshops, some semi-structured interviews were run, either in presence during the workshops or – in one case – through an online questionnaire. The interviews focused on the following questions:

I1: Workshop Interview guide – Teachers / staff**Joint workshop and L&T activities**

1. Were the learning activities within your institution (pre and post) well aligned with the joint workshop? Was there good integration of the L&T activities in your institution with those carried out collaboratively?
2. With hindsight, is there anything you would like to improve/ do differently?
3. What was the quality of the student outputs?
4. Have you changed or are you going to change anything in your teaching activities as a result of the workshop activities?
5. What did you like the most in the Annual Workshop? What did work well?
6. What would you suggest to change in the next Annual Workshops?
7. Did you tell about OIKONET to any colleague? Have you discussed it with your colleagues?

Semi-structured interviews for the evaluation of annual workshops by teachers and staff

3.3 Digital environment

The evaluation of the OIKONET digital environment was done through different activities:

1) After the first year of the project, data was collected from all project partners through an online survey in order to understand how much they used the different communication and sharing tools that were available to them, how useful they found them, and to get suggestions to improve the use of these tools. The tools that were considered in the online survey were the following:

- E-mail
- Newsletter
- Website
- Dropbox
- Google Docs
- Facebook
- Google+
- Twitter
- YouTube
- Blogs

The use of these tools was evaluated according to three criteria that correspond to three main communication goals: 1) receiving / getting information about the project, 2) communicating and collaborating with project partners and students, and 3) promoting the project to the outside.

For the abovementioned tools the following questions were asked:

<p>In the first year of the project, how often have you used <i>tool XYZ</i> for the following tasks?</p> <p>A) To receive information/updates on OIKONET B) To communicate with OIKONET partners and students C) To promote OIKONET to the outside</p> <p>(Options: Daily / Weekly / Monthly / Less than once per month / Never)</p>
<p>How useful is <i>tool XYZ</i>...</p> <p>A) To receive information/updates on OIKONET B) To communicate with OIKONET partners and students C) To promote OIKONET to the outside</p> <p>(Options: Very useful / Useful / Not very useful /Not useful at all / N/A)</p>
<p>Do you think that the chosen tools are used in an efficient way? Do they efficiently support communication? (Open question)</p> <p>Do you have any suggestions on how to improve communication and document sharing in general? Are there other tools that could be useful? (Open question)</p>
<p>Gender (female / Male) Institution (open text) Name (open text)</p>

For some tools, some specific questions were added and / or changed (e.g., for the newsletter, for Dropbox and Google Docs), in order to understand more clearly how those tools were used.

The questionnaire was answered by 25 project members.

2) Two analyses of the actual usages of the various tools were carried out at the half (month 18) and at the end (month 36) of the project. The usage analysis took into consideration the following tools (for each tool, different indicators were considered, depending on the available data):

- OIKONET website (source: Google Analytics): numbers of sessions, users, page views; countries of origin; devices; sources of traffic; most visited pages.
- OIKONET blogs: number of posts and of comments received; number of contributors.
- OIKONET Newsletter (source: MailChimp): number of recipients for each issue, number of recipients who opened and clicked on links, numbers of clicks on links; most clicked links.
- OIKONET Facebook page (source: Facebook Insights): number of likes on page; number of published posts, number of likes, sharing and comments on posts, number of impressions, visualizations and on engagements on average for each post.
- OIKONET Facebook groups: number of members for each group, number of posts and of contributors, number of likes and of comments on posts.
- OIKONET Twitter channel: number of followers; number of tweets, number of retweets and of favourites on tweets; use of relevant hashtags.
- OIKONET YouTube channel: number of subscribers to the channel; number of videos published; number of views received by videos.
- OIKONET Google+ community: number of members, number of posts, number of contributors.

3) An analysis of the usability of the OIKONET web portal was performed after the second year of the project (month 24). The goal of the usability analysis was to detect some of the possible problems and obstacles that may hinder visitors of the OIKONET web portal (www.oikonet.org) in achieving their goals.

The analysis was conducted through activities of user testing: selected users (in this case teachers and/or researchers in the field of Architecture or Urban Design) were asked to perform some tasks on the OIKONET web portal, while an OIKONET project partner acted as expert/inspector monitoring them and evaluating if they could complete the assigned tasks.

34 usability tests were done by 27 different partner institutions. Furthermore, at USI 5 additional usability tests were done by using an eye-tracking tool: users were asked to solve the tasks while being monitored by a hardware that tracked their eye movements on the screen.

3.4 Evaluation of external experts

Following the recommendation of the EACEA after the OIKONET Progress Report, **two external experts** were invited to review some project activities:

- **Prof. Flora Samuel**, Professor of Architecture and the Built Environment at the University of Reading (UK);
- **Prof. Constantin Spiridonidis**, Architect and Urban Planner, Ph.D. in Architecture and Urban Design, teacher of “Urban and Architectural Design Theories and Design” at the School of Architecture of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece.

Flora Samuel attended the second International conference and the second project general meeting that in Bratislava (September 24-25, 2015) and the third international conference and the third project general meeting in Manchester (September 22-23, 2016); she delivered a first feedback report on December 15, 2015 and a second one on October 22, 2016. Constantin Spiridonidis attended the fifth meeting of the sub-network “Pedagogical activities” in Brussels (January 22, 2016) and delivered his feedback report on April 28, 2016.

Before the international conference and project general meeting in Manchester, the OIKONET Steering Committee produced a report with the answers to the comments and remarks presented in the reports of the external evaluators (not including the second report by Flora Samuel).

The main findings emerged through these evaluation activities are presented in Chapter 4 of this deliverable; the reports of Flora Samuel and Constantin Spiridonidis and the report with the answers of the OIKONET Steering Committee are attached to this deliverable as Annexes 2, 3, 4 and 5.

3.5 Final evaluation activity

During the last project general meeting, one session was dedicated to an activity of evaluation of the project by all partners. Goal of the activity was to have all project partners reflect backwards on the three years of the project, on what went well, on what could have been done better, on what they bring home from the project, as individual partners and as institutions.

The activity was divided into some separate tasks:

- “What do you bring home from the OIKONET project?” Each partner individually writes on a sticker 1 to 3 things s/he brings home from the project (something s/he has learnt, has found particularly useful, will use/adopt in the future, etc.), one thing per sticker (15 minutes).
- Divided into groups of 4 to 5 partners of the same sub-network, participants answer the following questions, writing one answer per sticker (stickers of different colours for the different questions):
 - What went well in our sub-network?
 - What did not work well / could have been done better in our sub-network?

- What went well in the interaction with the other sub-networks?
- What did not work well / could have been done better in the interaction with the other sub-networks?
- What can we do to keep the network active? (30 minutes)
- Partners assign each sticker to one of the 9 project objectives. For each project objective, an A3 sheet was prepared, under which partners had to attach the stickers. (15 minutes).
- Plenary discussion on the main results emerging from the stickers and on the possible activities to keep the network active after the end of the project (30 minutes).

OIKONET partners during the final evaluation activity

The main findings of this reflection and evaluation activities are presented in the next chapter of this deliverable.

4 MAIN FINDINGS FROM EVALUATION ACTIVITIES

The detailed results of the evaluation activities can be found in Deliverables 6.2, 6.3, 6.4 and in all the single reports that have been produced. We present here only a summary of the main findings that emerged from all the activities.

4.1 Main findings from the evaluation of events: meetings and international conferences

Generally speaking, **sub-network and general meetings** have been highly appreciated, as participants found them useful, productive and inspiring. The following graph, included in Deliverable 6.2, shows the overall meeting scores for all the sub-network meetings.

Figure 1. Overall meeting scores for all the sub-network meetings.

As it can be seen, participants' satisfaction is generally high, with some peaks in 4 meetings, where the average score is higher than 8, 50/10, and 2 meetings that were less appreciated (average score lower than 7, 50/10).

As regards the evolution of each subnetwork, it can be noticed that in WP2 (red columns) high expectations were present in the first two meetings, then a kind of crisis happened in the middle of the project, finally participants' satisfaction went upwards again; in WP3 (blue columns), aside from the meeting in Rimini, which was exceptionally good, a steady progression can be observed; finally, WP4 has maintained more or less the same level throughout all the project.

Some problematic issues that emerged in the earlier meetings could be solved during the project: for instance, the definition and selection of adequate communication tools that could support the communications and collaboration practices of such a large network emerged as an issue in the earlier meetings, while it was not mentioned anymore in the last meetings.

One problematic aspect that could not be completely solved was the unbalance in the engagement of partners: not all partners have been equally engaged and active in the meetings nor in the project, and this emerged in the feedbacks from project partners also in the second half of the project.

Also the **international conferences** have been highly appreciated, mainly because they provided interesting opportunities for networking and promoted a change in the professional practices of participants. The selection of topics and the choice of the keynote speakers in all three conferences were particularly appreciated; on the other side, the general quality of the presentations in the conferences was not always evaluated as high. Finally, in the first two conferences, almost all participants were project partners, but this changed in the third conference, which was attended by a higher number of external participants.

4.2 Main findings from the evaluation of learning activities

In general, for both students and teachers the collaborative **learning spaces** with the involvement of participants from different institutions and countries was a **positive experience**. The expectations of students about the collaborative learning spaces were mostly concerned with **networking, collaboration and sharing**. Hence, the importance of accurately planning and structuring the online collaboration, which in some cases should have been done better; on the contrary, in presence collaborations and group works during the international workshops has always been very much appreciated.

With regard to the online learning spaces, students and teachers considered the OIKODOMOS Workspaces an inspiring learning and teaching environment, but stressed the importance of including training sessions to learn about the environment at the beginning of each course. Students appreciated also the **task-based structure** of the workspaces and found it a good way to share projects, view other students' projects and provide critical opinion on the works of others. The **use of additional communication tools** (e.g. chats, Facebook, Twitter ...) allowed further enhancing the learning experience, as they facilitated direct exchange between participants.

The **preparatory activities to the workshops** have played an important role in preparing students to the workshops. Hence, again, the importance to plan them accurately and to align them very well with the workshop theme. During the workshops, the **site visits** and the **social events** were appreciated very much, too.

The learning activities promoted within OIKONET have also been used as a **space for experimentation**: during the Cottbus and the Belgrade workshops, for instance, alternative ways of presenting the final group works were experimented, such as the use of an informal poster session and a wrap-up session in Cottbus and a role play in Belgrade. Similarly, some teachers tried to implement slightly different formats of Learning Spaces by for example using different technological tools and by engaging students and institutions in a different way (e.g., in the second edition of the Learning Space “Small is Power”, where students were asked to work on the modelling task right from the beginning and throughout the whole course instead of adding it as final task; or in “Thinking Dwelling”, which aimed at creating a shared learning space on housing and dwelling across subject-matters and institutions).

Finally, the **definition of specific expected learning outcomes** during the preparation phase of the workshops and of the Learning Spaces, helped both students and teachers to focus on the most important goals of the learning activities and facilitated the final evaluation of students works.

4.3 Main findings from the evaluation of the digital environment

The results of the different evaluation activities that were conducted on the OIKONET digital environment show that there has been a continuous improvement under different aspects:

- From a technical point of view, the OIKONET website has been continuously refined and improved, also thanks to the results of the usability analysis that was conducted at the end of the second year of the project (see also Deliverable 5.1); for instance, menus and sub-menus have been redesigned, the overlapping of News and Activities sections has been resolved, some graphical adjustments have been introduced, and so on.
- From the point of view of the availability of tools for communication and collaboration, while at the beginning of the project too many tools were in use, thus making it difficult for partners to understand which tools were used for which purposes, after the first year a selection of communication and sharing tools was made. This helped partners to use more effectively and efficiently the proposed tools, although in some cases not all difficulties have been overcome (e.g., after the shift from Dropbox to Sharepoint, some partners continued to have problems in using it properly).
- From the point of view of the use of the different tools, some good practices clearly emerged, like the use of some social networking tools (blogs, Facebook groups, YouTube channel) as a support for learning activities (international workshops or learning spaces). Furthermore, the analysis of visits to the website and of engagements in the social networks related to the project shows that during the major project's events (international workshops, international conferences) the online communication activities had peaks.

The main unresolved critical point about the use of digital tools regards the use of social networks for activities of promotion and dissemination of the project's results, which has remained limited, although partners considered them as useful tools, as it emerged from the survey done after the first year. Tools like the OIKONET Facebook page and the OIKONET Twitter and YouTube channels could have been exploited more extensively and more regularly to promote the project outside the network of the partners, as observed also by prof. Flora Samuel in her first review as an external expert.

4.4 Feedback from external experts

In their three reports, the external experts (Prof. Flora Samuel, through two reports, and Prof. Constantin Spiridonidis, in one report) highlighted both the positive aspects of the functioning of the project and some critical remarks.

The positive aspects can be summarized in the following main points:

- The project is very well organised and coordinated, developed with coherence, enthusiasm and very systematic steps; the leadership of the project is strong, well organized, self-critical and transparent.
- The network that has been created through the project is mature; the project has been an overwhelming success in terms of making a network and spawning new networks and connections.
- The team made a really important contribution to the way in which the field of global dwelling will develop in future.
- Group dynamics are excellent and inclusive.

- Internal assessment has been done through a systematic and serious approach, as it can be seen – for instance – with the evaluation of the digital platform, which was done through innovative and sophisticated digital techniques.
- In terms of academic outputs, the project team is taking a lead.
- The learning activities are supported by a very strong idea about the impact, the advantages and the value of collaborative actions, and are organized in a way that grants them flexibility and facilitates the involvement of the contributing teaching staff.

The critical aspects that were highlighted by the external experts can be summarized as follows:

- The dissemination of project results, in particular to the housing and architecture community, is one weak point of the project. The project team is aware of a lack of public awareness of OIKONET and of the need to engage with more stakeholders outside academia.
- Due to the funding framework of the project, much of the energy of the group was dissipated within procedures and bureaucracy, when it could have been used more creatively to develop collaborative research and allow for more substantial discussions. As a matter of fact, some project activities seem to be developed in a fragmented and patchy way – i.e., not in connection with other partners or activities – namely some learning activities and some exploitation activities.
- Some members complained of not having time allocations which were adequate to really address the tasks that they were set. More time would have allowed better integration between the three subnetworks: there was cross-collaboration and support, but it was not sufficient. WP2 played a particularly important role in fostering cross-communication across the subnetworks: some of its activities developed some really fruitful work, although it did not get as far as the team had perhaps hoped.
- Communication was also an issue for the project, as some partners had difficulties to work and communicate in English.

The remarks made by the external reviewers were answered and discussed in the report with the answers of the OIKONET Steering Committee, which is attached to this deliverable, together with the three reports, as Annexes 2, 3, 4 and 5.

4.5 Main findings from the final evaluation activity

The following pictures show how participants distributed their reflections on what they bring home from the project and on what worked well and what could have been done better in their sub-networks and in the interaction with the other sub-networks (see paragraph 3.6), assigning each of them to one of the nine main project's objectives:

1. Facilitate the *exchange of experience and knowledge* across the partnership.
2. *Collaboratively design learning activities* around problems addressing different dimensions of housing.
3. Overcome the boundaries between *on-site and on-line* learning spaces.
4. Create a *cross-institutional, cross-disciplinary network* of learning activities focused on contemporary housing.
5. Establish procedures to facilitate the *long-term collaboration* of higher education institutions dealing with contemporary housing problems.
6. Consolidate and expand the *OIKODOMOS digital platform*.
7. Contribute to the *solution of contemporary housing problems*.

8. **Engage citizens** in the processes of defining and solving problems concerning dwelling and the living environment.
9. **Engage countries outside Europe** in the discussions about contemporary housing problems, in partnership with EU countries.

Distribution of the stickers through the 9 project objectives during the final evaluation activity.

As it can be seen at a first glance, some objectives have been taken into consideration by project partners much more than others; and some objectives have been more “problematic” (pink stickers), while others have received more positive inputs (green stickers).

Objective 1 (*Exchange of experience and knowledge*) received the highest number of stickers: the exchange was the most relevant aspect for many participants in the project. Among the things that participants bring home from OIKONET, they mentioned “a network of friends, partners and opportunities”, the possibility to compare “experiences and approaches”, the “exchange of experience and ideas in WP meetings”, a “new interdisciplinary knowledge on housing”, the “International OIKONET Conference”, the “MOOC environment”, and others.

Among the things that worked well about the exchange of experience and knowledge, participants mentioned the conferences and the international workshops, the activity of commenting on the Housing Research Readers, the definition of global dimension of housing, the online seminars in the Learning Spaces, and others.

A few things that did not work well in the exchange of experience and knowledge were also mentioned: the communication of contents and the establishing of shared understanding, the weak interaction with other groups, and not meeting the deadlines.

Objectives 2 (*Collaboratively design learning activities*) and **4 (*Cross-institutional, cross-disciplinary networking*)** have proved to be very relevant for participants, because learning activities played a pivotal role in the project and involved a majority of partners. All three objectives received many stickers from participants. Interestingly, objective 2 (“Collaboratively design learning activities”) received only “positive” stickers, i.e., stickers about things that participants bring home from the project and about things that worked well, such as “a new understanding of how to organize and prepare learning”, the “importance of integrating research with pedagogic activities”, the good results obtained in the Learning Spaces, the experience of the development of the MOOC, and so on.

On the contrary, for **objectives 3 (*On-site and on-line learning spaces*)** and **4 (*Cross-institutional, cross-disciplinary networking*)** some things that did not work well were mentioned, thus showing that in the creation of blended and cross-institutional and cross-disciplinary learning activities partners encountered some problems. For instance, participants mentioned the lack of follow-up activities after the workshops, the difficulty to integrate the online activities in the regular curricula of each institution, the difficulty for some students in preparing for the workshops, the disparity in the quality level, the difficulty to interact with the partners of other subnetworks, the need to have more meetings, the difficulties in using the online environments. Among the positive aspects that were mentioned under these two objectives, it is worth reporting here the creation of new personal and professional contacts and of networks of collaboration, the interaction and the team cohesion, the international workshops, new ways of learning and communicating ideas, and others.

Also for **objective 5 (*Long-term collaboration*)** some problematic aspects were mentioned, such as the disparity in level of engagement among project partners, the lack of interaction in the activities of the subnetwork Community Participation (WP3), and the difficulties in the collaboration in the Learning Spaces.

Not surprisingly, as objective 5 dealt with long-term collaborations, this objective received the highest number of suggestions of activities to keep the networks alive in the future (blue stickers): Erasmus exchanges, define the niche for OIKONET, find proper funding, define the expected activities of the network, keep the sub-networks alive, continue existing bilateral collaborations, continue workshops and conferences, continue research collaborations.

Also **objective 6 (*Digital platform*)** received a couple of suggestions to keep the network alive: maintain the digital platform, particularly Oikopedia, and encourage the network members to continuously refer their students to the OIKONET digital environment.

Objectives 7 (contemporary housing problems) and **8 (engaging citizens)** regarded the project's contributions to **solve contemporary housing problems**, also with the help of citizens. Both objectives received only “positive” stickers and suggestions, mentioning the publications, the Oikopedia, the different multidisciplinary approaches, the workshops and the corresponding topics, the collaboration between the pedagogic and the community participation sub-networks, the case studies that were introduced in the workshops.

Finally, **objective 9 (engaging non-European countries)**, received only 2 stickers, thus suggesting that this objective has not been considered as a priority by project partners.

4.6 Impact of the project

The answers of project partners to the first question in the final evaluation activity (“What do you bring home from the OIKONET project?”) show clearly that the project has had an important impact, at least at the level of their individual professional practices, and in some cases also at the level of their institutions. In their answers participants mentioned many different things they bring home from the project, at different levels:

- Networking: “Collaborations with other institutions”, “A network of friends, partners and opportunities”, “Collaboration”, “Big, reliable and diverse network”, “Positive connections to other housing researchers throughout Europe, that will last far beyond the OIKONET project”, “A possible future research net”, and others;
- Learning and teaching practices: “Peer engagement useful for my teaching”, “Learning design as a way of preparing a course”, “A new understanding of how to prepare and organise learning”, and others;
- Knowledge sharing and pedagogic innovation: “OIKONET project helps us to widen our view on sustainable buildings (from different point of view)”, “New interdisciplinary knowledge on housing”, “the concept of dwelling and participation when constructing built environment has deepened”, “Comparing experiences and approaches”, “Converting research findings into pedagogical practice”, “New relevant ideas for housing research”, “A whole new knowledge of blended learning”, “Multidisciplinary approach”, and others.

The issue of impact has been dealt also by Flora Samuel in her “OIKONET Final External Assessor Report”, where she observed:

“Reflecting back on the project the members identified a need for a greater focus on policy or at least the inclusion of targets that related to policy impact. Global Dwelling, before OIKONET, was such a diffuse area that it is difficult to conceive how this might have been done. After the project the way in which to influence policy seem to be far clearer. The group could, for example, lobby to change the criteria of architectural education, soon up for review, to ensure that participatory practice, research and global dwelling become a required part of architectural training” (see Annex 5).

Constantin Spiridonidis stressed the importance of clearly defining the target groups of the different project's activities in order to clearly define the impact:

“It would be an added value of the work in the Project if the team could clearly define the impact of the outcomes on the different targets of the actions. The outcomes of the Project are addressed to different target groups and this affects the development of the outcomes. The more clearly defined the target groups are, the more efficient the development processes of the project's actions development and the impact of their outcomes will be” (see Annex 3).

Finally, a question about the impact of the project onto participants' teaching, research or working practices was present in the questionnaires distributed at the end of the three international conferences. In all cases, most participants confirmed that attending the conference invoked a change in their practices: 22 out of 26 respondents in the conference in Barcelona, 10 out of 18 in Bratislava, 21 out of 22 in Manchester. The changes that were mentioned by participants regarded the integration of new tools, approaches, topics and resources that were presented at the conference into their teaching and/or research practices, the development of new collaborative activities with partners, and a better integration of research, education and community research.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The quality of the OIKONET project has been assured through a systematic evaluation of the different realms of the project, as planned in Deliverable 6.1 “Evaluation plan”. The evaluation activities have been performed by the evaluation team together with all project partners. In addition, two external experts have provided their feedback about some activities and some processes of the project.

In these conclusions, we will compare the evaluation activities that have been actually carried out with those planned in the evaluation plan, explaining the reasons for the (slight) deviations that have occurred, and present some final reflections on the evaluation activities and processes of the project.

5.1 Deviations from evaluation plan

The following deviations from the Evaluation plan (D6.1) have occurred:

- Evaluation of events:
 - Only one participatory action (in Rimini) has been evaluated by the evaluation team, and no exhibitions; this was due to the difficulties in exchanging information with the promoters of the events.
 - In addition to the subnetwork meetings, also the three general meetings have been evaluated.
- Evaluation of learning activities:
 - The two editions of the MOOC have been evaluated internally by the development team.
 - The evaluation of the Learning Spaces have always been done with students, in some cases also with teachers.
 - More Learning Spaces than originally planned have been evaluated, and in some cases multiple editions of a Learning Space have been evaluated.
- Evaluation of the digital environment:
 - Analysis of usages of the OIKONET digital environment has been extended to all social media (Facebook, Twitter, YouTube), not only to the website and blogs.
 - Usability analysis has been done on all the website, also through eye-tracking.

5.2 Final reflections on evaluation activities and lessons learnt

The main lessons learnt from the evaluation activities can be summarized around the following points:

- **The participation of the project partners in the evaluation activities has been generally high.** The rate of responses to the questionnaires, for instance, has been in general high, although not equally distributed among all project partners: some partners have always answered surveys, others hardly any. Specifically, the surveys to collect the students’ feedback at the international workshops have always had very high response rates, also because during the workshops some time was specifically allocated for this activity. In other cases, the response rate was good but could have been better.

- **The results of the evaluations have often been used to improve and refine other project activities.** For instance, the students' feedback about the first international workshop in Lisbon has been very useful to organize the following workshops, making the needed changes to the organization, to the program, and so on; the partners' feedback about the communication tools has led to the selection of the most useful tools; the results of the usability analysis on the OIKONET website have been used to update and refine it; and so on.
- From the point of view of the **methods and the tools** that have been used for the evaluations, it can be observed that the use of both online and paper survey depending on the different situations was useful. On the other side, most feedback was provided through structured surveys: in some cases, it would have been more useful to do (semi-)structured interviews or focus groups with some selected participants, in order to gain more in-depth insights about the activities under evaluation. Unfortunately, this has often not been possible, because it would have required an additional effort on the side of both the evaluators and the project partners, who have already been exposed to many requests for feedback about many activities.
- Finally, the importance of **involving the evaluation team in the planning of project activities** that have to be evaluated emerged clearly during the project. This happened, for instance, in the evaluation of learning activities, where the interaction between the evaluation team and the teachers involved in the learning activities improved over time, thus leading to a real co-design of the evaluation questionnaires. In other cases, the lack of regular interactions resulted in the difficulty for the evaluation team to know who was doing what and when, and thus to plan evaluations properly. To get to a better interaction between the evaluation team and the leaders of the collaborative learning activities it is important to increase the awareness of the importance of evaluation activities among partners.

6 APPENDICES

6.1 Appendix 1 – Evaluation questionnaire for the Belgrade international workshop

QUESTIONNAIRE						
<p>This questionnaire is to help us refine the learning activities, processes and environments of OIKONET. Your responses will be entered anonymously into a database and analysed. The results will be published on a report on the project web site, www.oikonet.org.</p>						
About you:						
1. Nationality: _____						
2. Sex: <input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female						
3. Institution: _____						
4. Which Course are you on:						
Level of study: <input type="checkbox"/> Bachelor <input type="checkbox"/> Master <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____						
Year of study: <input type="checkbox"/> 1st <input type="checkbox"/> 2nd <input type="checkbox"/> 3rd <input type="checkbox"/> 4th <input type="checkbox"/> 5th <input type="checkbox"/> Other _____						
5. What is your level of proficiency in English?						
<input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Basic <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Very good <input type="checkbox"/> Native speaker						
Learning Experience <p>In this part we would like you to evaluate the learning experience AS A WHOLE; please, consider the preparatory activities in your institution and the workshop activities in Belgrade TOGETHER.</p> <p>A = Fully agree, B = Agree, C = Disagree, D = Fully disagree, N/A = Not Applicable).</p> <p>We would appreciate any comments giving more information about the reasons for your score.</p>						
6.	What were your expectations regarding this learning experience?					
7.	To what extent have these expectations been met?					
	<input type="checkbox"/> Only partially <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat <input type="checkbox"/> Fully met <input type="checkbox"/> It exceeded my expectations					
	<i>Comments (to question 7)</i>					
8.	From the beginning I was clear about the competences or learning outcomes to be gained from participating in this learning experience	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
9.	How well do you feel you have achieved the following learning outcomes?					
	a. I am able to understand the differences between various approaches to make cities liveable, such as regeneration, renewal and revitalization.	A	B	C	D	N/A

	<i>b. I am able to identify the specific characteristics of an area which embodies a potential for future change.</i>	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>c. I am able to develop a multi-dimensional analysis focusing on environmental, social and psychological aspects of liveable cities</i>	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>d. I am able to understand the importance of climate change as a driving factor to make cities more liveable, renewable and responsive to environmental challenges.</i>	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>e. I am able to propose strategies to revitalise and regenerate cities which allow for the participation of local community representatives.</i>	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>f. I am able to co-operate with team members, communicate my ideas and present them to others making an effective use of visual media.</i>	A	B	C	D	N/A
	Comments					
10.	What was your most important or interesting learning?					
11.	I had enough time to do the work	A	B	C	D	N/A
	Comments					
12.	The preparatory activities were well aligned / integrated with the activities carried out during the workshop in Belgrade	A	B	C	D	N/A
	Comments					
13.	Did teachers / students of other universities comment on the outcomes of your preparatory activities?					
	<p>a) Online, on the workspace "Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating livable cities" ? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>b) In person, during the workshop, after the presentation of your work? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No</p> <p>If yes, did you find their comments useful? What did you learn from them?</p>					
14.	Estimate how much you have used the following tools before and/or during the workshop					
	Tool	Very low usage	Low usage	High usage	Very high usage	
	Workspace "Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating livable cities"					
	Facebook Group "OIKONET Workshop Belgrade 2016"					
	Workshop Blog					
	Google Maps, Earth, Street View...					
	Other Internet Research Tools					
	Other Communication tools (e-mail / chat / ...)					
	Other (please, specify)					
	Comments					
15.	Using these tools I was able to access enough information to prepare for and work efficiently during the workshop in Belgrade	A	B	C	D	N/A

	<i>Comments</i>					
16.	The whole learning experience was positive / good	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
17.	What did you like? What was done well?					
18.	What could be done differently?					
19.	This learning experience is worth being repeated in the future	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
<p>Preparatory Activities</p> <p>Before the workshop in Belgrade, you were asked to carry out some preparatory activities in the online learning environment OIKODOMOS Workspaces “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating livable cities”.</p> <p>In this part, we would like you to focus ONLY on these PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES.</p> <p>A = Fully agree, B = Agree, C = Disagree, D = Fully disagree, N/A = Not Applicable</p> <p>We would appreciate any comments giving more information about the reasons for your score.</p>						
20.	In the Workspace “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating livable cities” the tasks /learning activities were relevant and clear	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
21.	The sequence of tasks / learning activities was meaningful to me	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
22.	The task-based structure of the Workspace “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating livable cities” offered a coherent way of learning	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
23.	I got enough training to work efficiently with the learning environment of the Workspace “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating livable cities”	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
24.	I have read most of the documents that were provided through the Workspace “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating livable cities”	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
25.	The materials available in the Workspace “Renewing / Revitalizing: Creating livable cities” (reference literature, maps) were useful	A	B	C	D	N/A

	<i>Comments</i>					
26.	Interacting online with other students / teachers (e.g., in the Facebook group “OIKONET Workshop Belgrade 2016”) has been a good experience	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
27.	How could online interactions between students/teachers of other universities before the workshop be further improved?					
<p>Belgrade Workshop</p> <p>The following questions focus on the WORKSHOP in Belgrade and are related to the activities that have been carried out during the days of the workshop.</p> <p>A = Fully agree, B = Agree, C = Disagree, D = Fully disagree, N/A = Not Applicable</p> <p>We would appreciate any comments giving more information about the reasons for your score.</p>						
28.	The introduction / briefing sessions made all aspects of the Belgrade Workshop clear	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
29.	I am clear about the way in which my work will be assessed	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
30.	The lectures were well aligned with the workshop theme	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments (to question 30)</i>					
31.	Presenting the outputs of the preparatory activities on Monday was useful	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
32.	The site visit to Kosančićev Venac helped my work during the workshop	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
33.	The site visit to Belgrade Waterfront helped my work during the workshop	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
34.	The Studio activity was well aligned with the workshop theme	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
35.	The tutoring activities were useful for the work in the Studio activity	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
36.	The Interim Critique session on Wednesday was useful	A	B	C	D	N/A

	<i>Comments</i>					
37.	Working collaboratively with students / teachers from other countries has been a good experience	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
38.	The social events (group dinners, students' party, Mikser festival) helped breaking the ice and getting to know each other	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments (to question 38)</i>					
39.	I was able to communicate effectively with the other members of my group	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
40.	There was adequate access to computing resources	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
41.	I had enough free-time	A	B	C	D	N/A
	<i>Comments</i>					
42.	Do you have any other comments or suggestions regarding the learning experience as a whole?					
	Please return the completed questionnaire to Anna Picco-Schwendener or to your tutor. If you have any questions please contact Anna Picco Schwendener (anna.picco.schwendener@usi.ch).					
	Thank you very much for your time!					

6.2 Appendix 2 – First evaluation report by Prof. Flora Samuel

Scope

This qualitative review is based on the experience of attending the OIKONET meeting and the penultimate OIKONET conference Global Dwelling that took place in Bratislava 24-27 September 2015. The reviewer was also given access to a range of documents including the Internal Report of Project Activity (issue 4) dated 17.9.15. The project reports set out with clarity the achievements and activities of the network.

‘Promoting pedagogic innovation in the field of housing studies is the ultimate goal of OIKONET’. It will bring about change in the field of housing education through the creation of an ‘integrated team’ to create bridges between different fields and different geographies. OIKONET intertwines ‘three areas of activity each one making a subnetwork within the network’:

1. **Research** on housing studies from a multidisciplinary and global approach;
2. **Participatory actions** to engage communities in the definition, solution and evaluation of housing problems; and
3. **Pedagogical activities** which bring together different stakeholders, learning environments and disciplines.

These issues continue to be extremely timely and have much potential to impact positively on the Grand Societal Challenges.

This review will focus on the success of the network as a creative forum for change. A further final external review is anticipated which will drill down into its achievements as a whole. The reviewer also recognizes the constraints on the project based on its funding.

The inclusion of an external reviewer was suggested by the funders once the project was under way. It was not accounted for in the costings of the project and is therefore not funded in terms of time, hence the brevity of this report which provides a snapshot of the network at a particular moment.

Leadership

The network benefits from strong, well organized and self-critical, transparent, leadership, as was made evident in the introductory speeches to this well-structured event. Given the extent of the network it is not surprising that a minority of members are not contributing fully. The project leaders have clearly made every effort to encourage greater engagement from this group.

Network

The 35 network members are drawn from a remarkable variety of countries and backgrounds. When questioned about what they had gained from the project it became apparent that OIKONET had given them new perspectives and greater professional authority in their activities. Clearly OIKONET is now a mature network in which trust and respect have developed over time through careful leadership. Further project members expressed enthusiasm to keep working together after the end of the project. In these terms it has clearly been a great success.

Quality of Discussion

Plenty of time was allocated for discussion, workshops, interaction and brainstorming, perhaps in response to comments made by project members (see page 13, Internal Report 4). Clearly there is an excellent inclusive group dynamic with all members feeling supported to make contributions. Both the meeting and the conference were intellectually stimulating – with the

group are operating at the cutting edge of their field.

Quality of Conference

Keynote speakers were drawn from the Canada and UK bringing the attention of the group to examples of successful architectural research practice in the field of Global Dwelling. The open Call for Papers resulted in the selection of stimulating series of presentations from practitioners, academics, NGOs and others with a collective concern for wellbeing and housing. A strong presence of speakers from Eastern Europe was noted given the geographical position of the conference.

Internal Assessment

The reviewer met with the internal assessment team who have taken a systematic and serious approach to their task which is both complex and difficult. Clear measures of success are important for the future impact and development of the project and its sub-projects. A clear co-produced evaluation methodology is needed that extends to every area of activity. Ideally impact should be represented through infographics as is common in housing and architecture research.

The need to establish an evaluation template for the pedagogical workshops was discussed as attitudes to pedagogy vary greatly across the participating group. The assessment team was working on assessing the usability of the website, a key feature of the network. Network members were given guidance on how to participate in the survey at the Bratislava meeting. In terms of communication channels Facebook appeared to be working well for sharing information.

Given concerns over the non-participation of a minority group it would seem to be important to map the relative contribution of different members, perhaps starting with a self –evaluation, as it is important to understand reasons for non-contribution.

Data is needed on the effectiveness of the dissemination strategy. In particular Google Analytics on the usage of the website would provide important evidence of impact.

Dissemination

The project website provides a comprehensive overview of the very many outcomes achieved by the OIKONET team. It also gives access to the OIKOPEDIA resource which is developing well in multiple languages. Whilst social media may be working well internally there could be greater use of social media outwardly, for example through the Twitter feed. If there is any weakness in the project it is in its dissemination to the wider housing and architecture community as it is important to share further the important learning developed by the network, for example the online Housing MOOC. A final publicity push, involving all its members, is recommended as the project enters into its final stages. The final conference in Preston, UK promises to be excellent and could therefore form the nexus of a publicity drive.

In terms of academic outputs such as refereed journals the project team are clearly taking a lead. Network members could clearly be doing more to disseminate the scientific learning of the network through learned journals. This is a common problem in housing and architecture, field which look to the professional press more than academic publications and needs more work from all concerned.

Flora Samuel

15.12.15

6.3 Appendix 3 – Report by Prof. Constantin Spiridonidis

Prepared on behalf of the OIKONET Erasmus Network Project Financed by the European Commission through the Lifelong Learning Program (Project number 539369-LLP1-2013-1-ES-ERASMUS) the present external evaluation report concerns the activities of the Project presented and discussed in the fifth meeting of the subnetwork “Pedagogical Activities” that took place in Brussels, 22-23 January 2016. Even though the meeting primarily focused on the one of the three sub-networks of the project the WP4 “Pedagogical Activities”, some of the activities of other work packages were presented and discussed. The meeting was structured upon short presentations of the work done in the framework of the different activities of the Project followed by a discussion amongst participants. The objectives of the Meeting were to record the state of the art of the collaborative learning activities carried out in the winter semester; to report on the work done in WP6 on quality assurance, WP7 Dissemination and WP8 Exploitation; to elaborate proposals for the future activities of the Project. All the presented activities were under development so there were significant possibilities for the debates in the meeting and for this report to have an impact on the deliverables of the Project. The purpose of this evaluation report is to provide to the group a number of critical remarks the consideration of which could improve the already high quality of the Project’s promised deliverables.

1. Work Package 4: Pedagogical Activities

WP4 “Pedagogical Activities”, is composed by six collaborative learning spaces and three international workshops. The learning spaces are educational experiences developed in collaboration by a number of institutions over a common theme. This collaboration concerns educational activities tasks and expected outcomes developed in parallel by the participating institutions. The themes on which each learning space is dedicated are the following: Introduction to Housing, Habitat Regeneration Strategies, Threshold Matters, Housing Systems, Contemporary Living Patterns and Civic Housing.

The activities and the outcomes of this work package are supported by a very strong idea about the impact, the advantages and the value of collaborative actions to produce innovation, experimentation and multiplier effects towards more efficient teaching practices and learning processes. It still remains possible for the team to articulate the results and the outcomes of the activities of the WP in a way that a coherent result can emerge through the fragmented and introverted initiatives. Enthusiastic partners who evidently have worked hard to establish creatively a collaborative environment of experiences and knowledge exchanges compose the team of this work package. This gives to the Project the potential of further development and more advanced academic outcomes and results.

The quality of the work in the package could be further improved if some measures could be taken to the direction of more synergies between the actions, more coherence between their contents and more interaction between the partners for the assurance of the objectives set. More specifically the team is invited to consider the following critical remarks:

1.1. ‘Learning Spaces’

a. Structure of the ‘Learning Spaces’

A general remark concerning the contents of these learning spaces is that their themes have not a clear structure between them. They appear to have emerged by the specific interest of the participating staff without presenting a clear and coherent logic or position regarding their role in the education of the main topic of OIKONET Project. They do not appear as milestones of housing studies in higher education, or as distinctive steps in the development of knowledge skills and attitudes related to housing studies. However it is possible for the outcomes of the

collaboratively development of these modules to be easily organised under a coherent grid of themes, educational strategies and learning outcomes and priorities in order to be better capitalised in the future of the partnership.

b. Collaboration between ‘Learning Spaces’

Each one of the proposed learning spaces has an autonomous and introverted development. This is something that gives flexibility and in the same time facilitates the promotion of the contributing teaching staff academic interests. However, as there are certainly overlaps between the themes of the six learning spaces, it would be more interesting for the coherence of the work package, the group to consider the possibility of further collaborations between the learning spaces and to investigate the conditions and the means to assure such an objective.

c. Involvement of students

Each learning environment has its own internal form and principles of collaboration, which offers richness and openness to the Project. As this experience was rather new, it is easy to appreciate that the developed forms of collaboration would have different degrees of complexity, efficiency and performance. During the presentation at the meeting of the work in learning spaces, the comments expressed by the participated teachers about the proposed projects or other steps of the educational process of the modules appeared to be the most important vehicle for views, ideas and experiences exchange. It also appeared that the live communication developed during the semester concerned primarily coordination issues and less direct academic exchanges between the broader educational environments. The already gained experience can certainly give opportunities for more complex involvement of staff and students in this very important part of the academic identity of the OIKONET project.

d. Clarification of targets

In the description of the academic activities in learning spaces it is not clear if the target is the students, the teachers, the education strategy, the teaching method, the pedagogical objectives, the learning outcomes, the experimentation on housing design or the further investigation of the teaching subject. Even though all of them are present in each one of the learning spaces, it is important to establish a hierarchy and prioritize those who can efficiently develop in the short duration of a semester. The experience gained by the groups through the learning spaces can certainly help to define a clear educational strategy for these collaborative forms. Moreover, this will help to redefine the relationship between the six different learning spaces as it was mentioned above.

e. Impact on curricula

The ‘Learning Spaces’ are an established collaboration between existing modules, which eventually are adapted accordingly. It will be interesting for the groups to evaluate and enhance the impact of their activity in the curriculum of the institution they belong. More specifically it will be important to consider this impact first on other similar or related modules offered in the curriculum and second to the other modules of architectural theory and design. This could also be an activity subscribed in the logic of WP8 Exploitation.

f. Define the collective

The experience gained by these activities can give to the participant the opportunity to (re)define the collective and to further investigate its potential forms and practices in the further development of the objectives of the work package during and after the contractual period. Different forms of collaboration can support the investigation of teaching methods, of design and creativity investigations, of knowledge assurance or of attitudes developed.

g. Less complex MOOCs

The idea of the MOOC is an extremely important experiment, which gives an added value to the project and creates a significant basis for further development of similar initiatives. In case that the project will support similar initiatives it will be useful to narrow down the spectrum of the themes that an online module will cover and organise its contents with clearly defined expected outcomes, estimation of the ECTS on the basis of the time of student work and precise evaluation criteria of students' work.

1.2. Workshops

8. Synergies with 'Learning Spaces'

The three workshops proposed as extended parts of the activities of the WP4 are planned on the basis of specific predefined themes, which appear to be isolated from the issues and questions raised or set by the 'Learning Spaces'. Additionally these workshops are proposed also as part of the dissemination process, which can certainly be as such but not as their main purpose. However, it is possible to consider synergies between the two poles of this WP4 in order to overcome the apparent fragmentation and to establish a more synergetic logic in the common theme of WP4, which is the question of leaning.

2. Work Package 5 Digital Platform and Work Package 6 Quality Assurance

It is important to notice that the project has initiated a systematic evaluation process of the functionality of the digital platform, which constitutes a very important part of the successful development of the project. This evaluation is based upon innovative and sophisticated digital techniques from which the visibility, functionality and usability of the project's digital platform will be improved.

3. Work Package 7 Dissemination

There is a significant activity related to the dissemination initiatives of the Project. These activities are: The two Conferences organised by the Project, the publication of the proceedings, the development of social media like YouTube and Facebook, publications on local press and academic journals, exhibitions and newsletters. It seems that the dissemination remains active in that part of Project's life and will be completed by the end of the Project. There is a strong pressure by the coordinator to all partners to contribute to the dissemination of all completed activities in which they are involved.

An important position in the deassimilation of the Project is the under-preparation of Project's book, which will focus on new forms of learning housing at a global scale. This book can become another articulating mechanism of the outcomes of the three main subnetworks of the Project (Housing research, pedagogical activities and community participation) since learning could concern the new knowledge through research, the new experiences through participation processes and the pedagogical practices developed in higher education on this subject.

4. Work Package 8 Exploitation

The OIKONET Project proposed a coherent plan of exploitation activities which are organised on the basis of five deliverables presented under the titles: Network /Organisation Migration plan, Common Credits, Erasmus MUNDUS proposal, Community integration and Digital Platform. All these deliverables are under construction and preparation. The main concept of this exploitation plan is that it will emerge from the work done in the other work packages. In other words, the work packages will prepare the base and the main axes of the further exploitation of their outcomes. However it appears from the presentations during the meeting that the preparation of the deliverables of the exploitation package tend to lose touch from the

related work packages and are developed, to a certain extent, autonomously. It seems to be very important to (re)establish stronger synergies with the real laboratories of production of the material to be exploited since this will enhance the quality of the exploited outcomes.

5. Overall remarks

The OIKONET Project is very well organised and coordinated, developed with coherence, enthusiasm and very systematic steps. It certainly deserves the high grades gained by the EU services in its interim evaluation. It would be natural for the team to expect the same grades for the final report. There are some remarks that the team could take into account in order to assure more coherence between the actions of the Project and more consequence between its outcomes and objectives.

a. Coherence

As different groups develop the activities of the Project, it is observed that each team sets its own priorities, aims and criteria without examining their relation with the overall objectives of the Project. This has the risk to affect negatively the coherence of the Project, which was certainly one of the main criteria of the Project's award.

b. Synergies

A coherent proposal runs the risk to become fragmented if synergies between the different actions and outcome preparations are not encouraged. It is important for the group to work towards establishing synergies in all levels of the Project: Between the different sub-networks and work packages, between the different actions of the same work package, between the different steps and components of the same action. This will enhance the value of the collectivity that seems to be an important value for the partnership as it was very often mentioned in the presentations of the meeting.

c. Impact

It would be an added value of the work in the Project if the team could clearly define the impact of the outcomes on the different targets of the actions. The outcomes of the Project are addressed to different target groups and this affects the development of the outcomes. The more clearly defined the target groups are, the more efficient the development processes of the project's actions development and the impact of their outcomes will be.

Constantin Spiridonidis

6.4 Appendix 4 – Answers of the Steering Committee to the reports of the external evaluators

The answers of the members of the Steering Committee (Karim Hadjri, Leandro Madrazo, Henrich Pifko, Stefano Tardini, and Johan Verbeke), to the issues raised in the reports of the two external evaluators, Prof. Flora Samuel and Prof. Constantin Spiridonidis, were the following.

In the recommendations contained in the document “Approval of Progress Report”, sent to the project leader on June 11, 2015, the European Commission recommended to involve external experts in the project’s evaluation and quality assurance activities: “It is also highly recommended that the consortium uses evaluation processes that involve experts from external sources that operate outside of the project’s domain” (p. 4 of the LLP Progress Report Assessment Sheet). Following this recommendation, two external experts have been invited:

- Prof. Flora Samuel, Professor of Architecture and the Built Environment at the University of Reading (UK), is a well-known architectural historian. Her work focuses on Architects, their skills and how they communicate them to the outside world. A particular focus of her work are homes, housing and neighbourhoods in the UK and beyond. She was previously head of the School of Architecture at the University of Sheffield, from 2009 to 2013. She was elected National Member of RIBA Council in July 2014 and have led the RIBA Student Destinations Survey. Prof. Samuel attended the second International conference and the second project general meeting that were held in Bratislava on September 24-25, 2015, and delivered her feedback report on December 15, 2015.

- Prof. Constantin Spiridonidis is an Architect and Urban Planner and holds a Doctorate in Architecture and Urban Design. He teaches Urban and Architectural Design Theories and Design at the School of Architecture of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Greece. His research interests are in design theory, architecture and urbanism, architectural education and design pedagogy. He is involved in many academic initiatives in European at Intercontinental level, as well as European Union projects and committees related to architectural education. He has contributed as author or as editor to a large number of publications related to architectural education and the teaching of architectural and urban design. Prof. Spiridonidis attended the fifth meeting of the sub-network “pedagogical activities” that took place in Brussels on January 22, 2016, and delivered his feedback report on April 28, 2016.

The following summary includes some of the issues raised by the two reviewers and their corresponding reports (available as Annexes at the end of the document) as well as the answers of the OIKONET Steering Committee to their remarks.

Report by Prof. Flora Samuel

The review by Prof. Samuel focused “on the success of the network as a creative forum for change”.

She highlighted several positive aspects of the functioning of the network:

- The leadership is strong, well organized, self-critical and transparent, and has done every effort to try to involve in the network also that minority of members that are not contributing.

- Through OIKONET, the members of the network have gained “new perspectives and greater professional authority in their activities”, and expressed enthusiasm to keep working together after the end of the project. The network is now mature, in these terms OIKONET has clearly been a great success.
- Group dynamics are excellent and inclusive, both the meeting and the conference were intellectually stimulating.
- Internal assessment has been done through a systematic and serious approach.
- “In terms of academic outputs such as refereed journals the project team are clearly taking a lead”.

Likewise, the report included some suggestions and critical remarks:

- **It is suggested that a “clear co-produced evaluation methodology is needed that extends to every area of activity”, which could represent the impact of the project activities through infographics.**

ANSWER: the evaluation methodology was created at the beginning of the project, then refined and presented as Deliverable 6.1 attached to the Interim Report. In particular, the evaluation of the learning activities has been refined in strict collaboration with the teachers involved in them. The idea of representing the impact of the project activities through infographics is a good suggestion, which, however, must be confronted with the limited available resources.

- **It is suggested to map the different contributions of the network members, in order to highlight the members that are not contributing and understand their reasons.**

ANSWER: some tools are already in use for this, e.g. the “Project Work Log” (a sheet in the file “OIKONET Data Collector”, hosted on Google Drive) and the “OIKONET Activities Logs” (a file hosted on Google Drive), files where project members have to announce the different activities they have done for the project.

The logs that are inserted in these documents are used by the project leader to keep track of the project activities of each member; however, a systematic analysis and mapping of these logs has not been done.

- **It is argued that “data is needed on the effectiveness of the dissemination strategy”, suggesting using Google Analytics to assess the usage of the website.**

ANSWER: an analysis of the usage of the website through Google Analytics has been performed at the half of the project as part of Deliverable 6.4 and submitted as part of the Interim report. The analysis will be repeated at the end of the project.

The dissemination of project results, in particular to the housing and architecture community, is acknowledged as one weakness of the project (probably, the only one). It is suggested that social media could be used more outwardly and that more could be done “to disseminate the scientific learning of the network through learned journals”.

ANSWER: it is true that social media are being used more efficiently as internal communication tools (e.g., Facebook groups for supporting learning activities) and should be exploited more to disseminate the project’s results to the outside. As regards the dissemination to the housing and architecture community, the final conference of next September in Manchester will be an important occasion for this, as it is expected that several external academics, experts and practitioners will attend it.

Report by Prof. Constantin Spiridonidis

A purpose of Prof. Spiridonidis's review was to “to provide to the group a number of critical remarks the consideration of which could improve the already high quality of the Project's promised deliverables”.

He highlighted some positive aspects of the project:

- The activities and the outcomes of WP4 – Pedagogical Activities “are supported by a very strong idea about the impact, the advantages and the value of collaborative actions to produce innovation, experimentation and multiplier effects towards more efficient teaching practices and learning processes”.
- The learning spaces that have been activated have an autonomous development, which grants them flexibility and facilitates the involvement of the contributing teaching staff.
- The project's digital platform is being evaluated through a systematic process, “based upon innovative and sophisticated digital techniques from which the visibility, functionality and usability of the project's digital platform will be improved”.
- Overall, the “OIKONET Project is very well organised and coordinated, developed with coherence, enthusiasm and very systematic steps”.

Likewise, there were some suggestions and critical remarks:

- **It is suggested that the pedagogical activities are fragmented and introverted, each partner doing a particular program without having an overall plan that assures the coherence of the overall project and the fulfilment of the objectives for all activities.**

ANSWER: The themes of the learning spaces are suggested by partners, based on their own interests and curricula. Then, other partners might join the initiative on the same grounds: adequacy of the theme to their interests and curricula. In all learning spaces there have been involvement of different partners, although with a different intensity. At the most intensive level of collaboration, several partners have first agreed in the design of a common structure of learning activities and tasks, and then they have implemented them in a coordinated manner. Other partners having a less intensive involvement collaborate as external reviewers of critiques, or delivering some lectures.

What we want to achieve with this process is to enable the network members to develop their own ties based on their own interests. The results are the outcome of these networking. It was not the purpose of this project to provide an overall learning plan that should be fulfilled by the participants.

- **It is recommended to clarify the targets of the learning spaces since “it is not clear if the target is the students, the teachers, the education strategy, the teaching method, the pedagogical objectives, the learning outcomes, the experimentation on housing design or the further investigation of the teaching subject”.**

ANSWER: Every learning space is designed using a common template (i.e. a Learning Plan), where most of the abovementioned learning components are considered. See for example the learning plans of the learning spaces in the Appendices of Deliverable 4.1 Learning Spaces (http://arc.housing.salle.url.edu/oikonet-platform/public/upload/source/20150629082949_OIKONETD4.1Learningspacesv7.pdf)

- **It is contended that the themes of the workshops are not related to the issues and questions raised in the learning spaces.**

ANSWER: The theme of each workshop is proposed by the host partner, and then further elaborated with the collaboration of other partners. A workshop is a learning space in itself, composed of preparatory activities done distantly (as any other Learning Space, using the Workspaces environment) followed by the on-site activities during one week in the host institution. A workshop is an example of blended-learning, collaborative education model. Some work initiated in a workshop has derived in a learning program carried out as a MOOC

(http://www.oikonet.org/admin_controller/getDataElement/893/Learning%20space/a).

- **It is contended that the preparation of the deliverables of WP8 – Exploitation “tend to lose touch from the related work packages and are developed, to a certain extent, autonomously”.**

ANSWER: it was done what is possible to connect the activities of WP8 to the other work packages: in several sub-network meetings and in the second general meeting workshops were conducted to involve all project members in the reflection about the exploitation of the project outcomes. The deliverables of WP8 are all created starting from the input and materials provided by the partners working on the related work packages or through specific questionnaires, consolidating activities and material produced in other work packages.

Acknowledgments

The OIKONET Steering Committee would like to thank Prof. Flora Samuel and Prof. Constantin Spiridonidis for their feedback and suggestions, which have helped us to improve the outcomes of the project.

6.5 Appendix 5 – Second report by Prof. Flora Samuel

Context of Review

This qualitative review is based on the experience of attending the OIKONET meeting and the penultimate OIKONET conference Global Dwelling that took place in Bratislava 24-27 September 2015 and attendance at the OIKONET AGM at Manchester UK, 23 September 2017 which took the form of a very comprehensive feedback session including a large degree of healthy and reflective self-criticism as is evident from the extensive General Meeting 3 minutes which give a very accurate picture of this culminating moment.

An interim report was sent to the project team following the Bratislava meeting and the reviewer received back from the team a satisfactory response to the issues raised. ‘WP6 Answers to the Reports of the External Evaluators’. The reviewer was also given access to a range of documents including the Internal Report of Project Activity (issue 4) dated 17.9.15. The project reports set out with clarity the achievements and activities of the network.

The inclusion of external reviewers was suggested by the funders once the project was under way. It was not accounted for in the costings of the project and is therefore not funded in terms of time, hence it is not possible to provide a comprehensive review of all the group activities. Instead the focus is on the success of the project overall and the likely future of the network going forward.

Progress Against Oikonet Aims

‘Promoting pedagogic innovation in the field of housing studies is the ultimate goal of OIKONET’. It will bring about change in the field of housing education through the creation of an ‘integrated team’ to create bridges between different fields and different geographies. OIKONET intertwines ‘three areas of activity each one making a subnetwork within the network’:

1. **Research** on housing studies from a multidisciplinary and global approach;
2. **Participatory actions** to engage communities in the definition, solution and evaluation of housing problems; and
3. **Pedagogical activities** which bring together different stakeholders, learning environments and disciplines.

These issues continue to be extremely timely and have much potential to impact positively on the Grand Societal Challenges. One of the aims of the project was to increase awareness of global dwelling as an important issue. As participants at the AGM observed, maybe the whole process has been about understanding what global dwelling actually is.

In unpacking the field and presenting it as a series of threads of knowledge then tested through the project activities, the team have made a really important contribution to the way in which the field will develop in future. Focus should be given to disseminating what was learnt from disaggregating Global Dwelling in this way and what the project team learnt from it.

Network

Composition of the network. OIKONET includes a remarkable mix of expertise from a wide variety of backgrounds, industry, academia and NGOs all connected through the medium of the digital platform.

The members felt extremely positive about meeting people from all over the world with an interest in the same theme but addressing it from a wide variety of different perspectives. The project has been an overwhelming success in terms of making a network and spawning new networks and connections.

Workpackage 2 on research played a particularly important role in fostering cross-communication across the subnetworks. Here the creation of the framework, the OIKOPEDIA entries, the position papers and the mapping of the network's research has set the stage for developing some really fruitful work, although it did not get as far as the team had perhaps hoped.

Impact

Reflecting back on the project the members identified a need for a greater focus on policy or at least the inclusion of targets that related to policy impact. Global Dwelling, before OIKONET, was such a diffuse area that it is difficult to conceive how this might have been done. After the project the way in which to influence policy seem to be far clearer. The group could, for example, lobby to change the criteria of architectural education, soon up for review, to ensure that participatory practice, research and global dwelling become a required part of architectural training.

Dissemination

A remarkable collection of dissemination channels have been established under the auspices of the project which are set to be exploited in years to come.

- The OIKONET portal
- The Learning Spaces
- The Wiki / Oikopedia
- The MOOC
- The OIKOnetwork as semantic based environment
- The OIKONET blogs
- The case repository
- The Oikontology
- The Report on Learning spaces (Deliverable 4.1)
- The research readers
- The competence table for Global Dwelling (once D8.2 is established)
- The exhibition posters
- The conference proceedings
- The set of publications/papers
- The video materials
- The book (when finished)
- Best Practice in Community Integration (when D8.4 is established)
- The Facebook page (as a resource to contact the network)

- The Twitter channel
- The YouTube channel

It may be that there were too many channels of information given the allocated resources.

The innovative digital platform provides an extremely dense and novel body of information. Close inspection of the many outputs preserved for example in the research readers reveals many of them to be of an extremely high calibre. Some of the report documents could easily be translated into refereed journal outputs if time allowed.

The team are aware of a lack of public awareness of OIKONET and the need to engage with more stakeholders outside academia. I would say that this was a common problem in architecture based research projects as this is a field in which the divisions between academic research and practice are strong.

Lessons Learnt

Global Dwelling is a complex issue and participatory practice is a very time consuming way to work. In many ways the flaws of the project came from the framework within which it was funded which evidently led too much of the energy of the group being dissipated within procedures and bureaucracy when it could have been used more creatively to develop collaborative research and allow for more substantial discussions.

Members complained of not having time allocations which were adequate to really address the tasks that they were set and to complete dissemination. This may account for the slightly patchy levels of activity amongst the members. Members felt it would be more helpful in future to revise and adapt the aims to the timeframe or to spend more time developing collaboratively a framework for how to proceed at the start rather than have a rigid framework set up from the beginning.

More time would have allowed better integration between the 3 subnetworks. There was cross-collaboration and support but not sufficient (e.g. Research supporting Pedagogy such as the Cottbus workshop). Lack of time has made the developments of outputs such as refereed journal papers and the book more complex.

Communication was also an issue for the project. The need to work in English was difficult for some and the need to develop multiple translation formats was both costly and time consuming.

Future of the Network

The network members appear to be extremely positive about its future. Even without funding they were already planning a series of events and symposia to take the OIKONET momentum forward including another research workshop to be held in Ljubljana though quite how the momentum can be kept up without funding remains to be seen. Many that I talked to reported having lots of new ideas about what to work on next and how to develop the OIKONET learning.

A key issue is the relationship between OIKONET and other knowledge economies in the field, for example the European Network of Housing Research. Going forward it would seem important to build new synergies with other existing groups within and without Europe.

Options for further funding going forward include Erasmus+, Marie Curie ITN. Given the talent, determination and drive exhibited by the team the future of the OIKONET network appears to be assured

Flora Samuel

22.10.16